

THE INFLUENCE OF THE ALMALYK MINING AND METALLURGICAL COMBINE ON THE HYDROECOLOGICAL CONDITION OF THE AKHANGARAN RIVER

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Annotation: The article is devoted to the study of the influence of industrial wastewater from the Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Combine on the water quality of the Akhangaran River. It has been established that below the wastewater discharge, river water is contaminated with ions of various metals.

Keywords: Akhangaran river, Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Combine, water use, heavy metals, water quality, maximum permissible concentration.

Introduction: Water, as one of the main components of the natural environment, is crucial for ensuring life on earth. The problem of water resources and water quality, their determining role for the economy and the functioning of ecosystems, has now become particularly relevant, both in individual states and in the world as a whole.

In order to implement the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 3, 2002. No. 111 "On approval of the Regulation on State Monitoring of the Natural Environment in the Republic of Uzbekistan" over the past 15 years, a unified monitoring system has been created in the republic, a list of the main natural and man-made sources of environmental pollution has been formed, modern measurement methods have been developed, the material and technical base of eco-analytical laboratories has been modernized, for generalization and analysis of monitoring results The State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan for Nature Protection has established a state information and analytical center.

Assessment of the impact of wastewater on the condition of watercourses, timely identification and forecasting of the development of negative processes affecting the quality of water bodies in order to develop measures to prevent the harmful effects of these processes.

Making timely management decisions in the field of use and protection of water bodies. Improvement of the indicator of the water pollution index (IZV).

Analysis of the literature on the topic: The biological diversity of algae is determined by analyzing morphological features in combination with ecology and geographical distribution (Vinogradova, 1978).

The totality of algae species in a certain territory makes up its algoflora. The analysis of algoflora as a system of cohabiting and evolving populations of species according to B.A. Yurtsev (1968, 1982) is carried out on the basis of species diversity reflected in the list of flora. The main feature of algoflora is their diversity, therefore it is necessary to apply not only general approaches, but also a particular principle in the analysis of the floral system, identifying significant groups of species and evaluating the flora from the standpoint of the activity of species that reflect their ecology.

Ecological systems, as an even higher level of organization, include as interacting elements not only algae as living components, but also their habitat, expressed through hydrochemical and hydrophysical indicators.

In 2021, the Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Combine alone produced and enriched 35 million tons of ore by grinding and flotation. At the same time, an average of 4.5-5.0 m³ of water is required for each ton of ore, a total of 160 million m³ of water per year.

By 2027, the productivity of the Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Combine alone will triple, and it will have to process 100 million tons of ore per year.

So, by this period, the Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Combine alone will require an average of 480 million cubic meters of water [1, 2]. Therefore, the effective use of groundwater and surface waters, if necessary, the search for groundwater, the rational use of groundwater on mountain slopes remains one of the most pressing issues not only today, but also the near future. In particular, groundwater on the slopes of the Kalmakyr mine, the largest in Central Asia, causes the formation of various mine cracks and landslides. Many studies have been conducted on the effective use of such underground mining waters and their industrial applications [3, 4, 5, 6].

Materials and methods. The purpose of these studies was to study the water quality of the Akhangaran River, in the basin of which the largest enterprise in the republic for the extraction and extraction of various metals from rock – Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Combine (AGMK) operates. To achieve this goal, a set of hydrobiological methods was used, including field studies of the conditions of formation, purification and disposal of industrial and domestic wastewater, and water quality studies of water bodies.

Chemical and analytical analyses of selected river water samples were performed using generally accepted standard methods. Additionally, the results of analyses of water samples of the Akhangaran River for the content of heavy metals performed by the territorial bodies of state sanitary supervision over the past five years were used.

The assessment of the water quality of the Akhangaran River, carried out according to the ingredients normalized according to sanitary-toxicological and sanitary-chemical signs of harmfulness, revealed significant contamination of river water in the water use range located 1 km downstream of the river after the discharge of industrial wastewater.

Concentrations of toxic metals exceeded the established hygienic standards (MPC) for the content of lead, molybdenum, manganese, copper, iron, cobalt, zinc in water.

The calculation of the permissible levels of the total load of toxic metals on the reservoir according to the criteria of self-purification was carried out in accordance with the developed mathematical models with known values of multiple regression coefficients, it was found that the discharge of wastewater from AGMK will not adversely affect the process of biochemical oxygen consumption (BOD) if the concentration of copper in water is at the level of 0.33 mg/l (in 3 three times lower than the MPC). Concentrations of lead, zinc, iron, manganese, molybdenum and cobalt can be within the MPC.

According to the criteria of chemical oxygen consumption (COD), the concentration of lead in water should be below the permissible value of 3, zinc by 25, copper by 20, iron by 30, manganese by 1.7 and molybdenum by 12.6 times. Cobalt may be present in water at the level of its hygienic standard.

According to the criteria of ammonification and nitrification, data were also obtained indicating that the presence of toxic metals in water with their combined presence in water, even within the MPC, will not ensure the normal course of water self-purification processes.

In accordance with the requirements of the sanitary rules for the protection of surface waters from wastewater pollution (No. 0056-06, 2006) when several substances with the same limiting hazard index (HDL) are received The MPC of each of them should be reduced by the sum of the concentrations of these substances in the water. Taking into account these requirements, the values of the permissible content of toxic metals in their combined content in water are calculated.

Analysis and results

In the Akhangaran River water use range, safe water use conditions can be provided with a water content of zinc 0.04 mg/l, copper 0.05 mg/l, iron 0.01 mg/l, manganese 0.06 mg/l, molybdenum 0.02 mg/l. These values are, respectively, 12.5; 4.0; 6.0; 1.3 and 2.5 times lower than the MPC set taking into account HDL.

The values of lead and cobalt coincide with the standards of their content in water.

The content of lead, zinc, copper, manganese, molybdenum, and cobalt in the water of the Akhangaran River in concentrations exceeding acceptable levels causes the risk of developing various diseases in the population using river water for household and drinking purposes.

Significant air pollution of the atmosphere in the city of Angren and its surroundings NH_4 , CO, CO_2 , SO_2 , NO_2 , H_2S occurs during coal mining, natural underground fires of coal seams at the Angren brown coal deposit, as well as during coal burning at the Angrenskaya GRES and Novo-Angrenskaya TPP.

According to the data of the state agencies of nature protection [7], up to 1 million tons of harmful substances are released into the environment by enterprises of the city of Angren annually, of which: 37.7% are solid (dust and ash) and 64.3% are liquid and gaseous substances. Thus, in the valley of the Akhangaran River, 3 km from the Angren coal deposit, a halo of soils contaminated with heavy metals (Cu, Pb, Zn, Fe, Ni) was formed. High concentrations of lead and cadmium (350-500 mg/kg) were noted in the soil horizon, the same situation, a large halo of lead is observed near the Kalmakyr copper-molybdenum deposit (600-800 mg/kg), which exceeds the maximum permissible concentrations (MPC) by tens of times [4].

Conclusions. Thus, the Akhangaran River, used as a source of water supply and recreation, poses a potential danger to health due to the content of toxic elements in the water in quantities significantly exceeding acceptable levels. In many cases, the presence of toxic elements in water at the MPC level, taking into account the same limiting sign of harmfulness (HDL), does not provide safe conditions for water use, since the maximum permissible load (MPN) of metal ions according to the criteria of self-purification of water is set at lower limits.

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